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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE STRAIN
VARIATIONS IN THE PATIENTS OF RENAL COLIC AND
IDENTIFICATION OF RENAL COLIC DISPARITY
JUDGEMENT FEATURES**¹Dr. Farva Jamil, ²Dr. Aroosha Asif, ³Dr. Fatima Farooq¹House Officer in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.**Abstract:**

Objective: The main objective of the study was to analyze the strain variations in renal colic patients and to identify its character in disparity judgment of renal colic.

Methods: The study arranged for this purpose was of cross-sectional type. It was organized at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (June 2016 to August 2017). It consisted of patients with grumble telltale of renal colic and identified with a urinary pebble. The persons who were not identified with any disease and were healthy were also included in the study. These were added as a control group. The patients and the healthy persons were assessed according to the oxidative pressure specification. For mathematical evaluation, SPSS was used.

Results: Total of 83 individuals were added in the study. Out of these 50 were patients having renal colic while 33 were healthy person added as a control group. Out of 50 patients, it was calculated that half were males and half were females. In the control group person, the men were calculated to be 17 and women were 16. There were no notable variations in ages and femininity in the both healthy and control group. It was also noticed that there were no variations in oxidative pressures between both groups.

Conclusions: No addition of patients with oxidative pressure was found with renal colic. We can identify the various identifications of the abdominal hurt in patients with these conclusions.

Keywords: Oxidative Stress, Renal Colic.

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INTRODUCTION:

The most frequent cause of entrance of patients in an urgent situation sector is the renal colic because of urinary area stone. Constipation and other hindrance in the urinary tract are the general reasons for renal colic [1, 2]. A person felt most horrible pain suffering from renal colic. So, it should be managed as soon as possible. So, it is necessary to make a disparity verdict in a squat instant to remove other chances of the sting.

The stone of the urinary pathway starts from the kidney. After that, they spread into the ureter, bladder and urethra. The formation of stones in the proximal part of the urinary pathway is not too common. The chances of urinary pathway disorder according to literature were observed to be 12% – 15%. Multi-centre studies organized the incidence was calculated to be 14.8% [3, 4]. The cure for abdominal pain may be surgical or non-surgical according to the sternness of the disorder. If pain has been felt during renal colic, many reasons for pain in the abdomen were not included to make an analysis. Removal of pain completely in cases which are doubtful is dubious. Patients do not felt relieve due to these situations whereas ED physicians practice grief.

The complications showed by the individuals in the conditions of the severe appendix, peptic ulcer, gallstones with or lacking occlusion, serious renal artery embolism, abdominal aortic aneurysm ectopic pregnancy, ovarian cyst torsion, diverticular disease, bowel impediment and orchitis also resembles the complications of urinary shingle. If such type of signs appears in an individual it should be properly analyzed and tested [5]. The observers of the patients should be properly differentiated and analyzed their diseases by studying the previous history, physical appearance, time period when the signs start their appearance and they should analyze these patients tests in labs for further studies.

For identification of oxidative stress counting of overall antioxidant status, overall oxidant status and oxidative pressure would be more suitable. This is because the overall communications of these parameters give more suitable conclusions than the conclusions obtained during their separate impressions. Therefore, the factors that affect an overall conclusion due to unknown causes would not be added again [6].

It has been observed that the patients suffering from the severe appendix, abscesses, cancer, polycystic ovary syndrome etc have more chances to catch by the OS. The objective of the recent study was to

identify the OS parameters changed in renal colic. It was also identified the character of OS in the differentiating investigation of renal colic.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The study arranged for this purpose was of crosswise type. It was organized at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (June 2016 to August 2017). The patients who offered themselves with renal colic or the patients who were identified having urinary stone were added in the experiment. Control group was formulated by including healthy persons. The patients who were sure to ED with haematuria and renal colic, having no pain due to their clinical treatment and they have no reduction in the amount of urine output, were added as the cases. The persons selected for the control group were similar to patients in case of their ages, male or female, having no record of smoking or alcohol, having no heart problems, not undergone any type of therapy or surgery and they were not using any medicines since last 15 days.

Some type of patients who were already suffering from some disease like diabetes mellitus, chronic contamination, ischemic heart disease, congestive heart failure, acute pain in the abdominal area and patients who were using any type of medicines were not included in the study. The capacity of the study was told to all the subjects. And a hand-written approval was obtained from all subjects.

On the basis of OS constraint, the patients and control groups were evaluated. The blood of all the individuals included in the study was taken. The blood sample was collected by antecubital veins. These veins were centrifuged at 3000rpm for about 15 minutes. The temperature was maintained at about 37°C. Blood was transferred appropriately for the frosty sequence. The storage of erythrocytes was done at -80°C. After that it was identified for OS parameter. At institutional Central Laboratory, the biochemical tests were analyzed.

Typical protocols were calculated by using TAS, TOS and OSI [7 – 10]. SPSS was used to investigate the data. Percentages were compared by using the Chi-square test. The means of calculation between two groups were analyzed by using the Mann-Whitney test. The mathematically important value was considered to be $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Total of 83 persons were added in the study. In these persons, 50 were sufferers of renal colic and 33 were healthy individuals acting as control groups. 50 percent patients were male and 50 percent females. In

control groups 17 were male and 16 were female. Among the group of patients with renal colic mostly (64%) ages of the persons were between 20 to 40 while persons with ages between 40 to 60 were about 36%. There were 22 and 11 analogous integers among the control group. In age and gender, there was no specific variation was found.

(2.43 ± 0.29847) μ mol H₂O₂ equivalent /L were the average value of TOS in patients with renal colic. While (1.4573 ± 1.24177) μ mol H₂O₂ equivalent /L

was the average value among the healthy group. If we talk about the OSI the average value was found to be (0.4818 ± 0.60870) arbitrary unit in case of patients and (0.5988 ± 0.52079) arbitrary unit in a healthy group.

The measurement was also done in TAS, TOS and OSI Average rank and addition of rank and U values in both groups.

Table: Comparison of TAS, TOS and OSI Mean Rank and Sum of Ranks and U values between patients and control group

Groups		Number	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	U	P-Value
TAS (μ mol Trolox equivalent/L)	Renal Colic	50	40.87	2043.5	768.5	0.597
	Control	33	43.71	1442.5		
TOS (μ mol H ₂ O ₂ equivalent/L)	Renal Colic	50	39.98	1999	724	0.341
	Control	33	45.06	1487		
OSI (arbitrary unit)	Renal Colic	50	39.58	1979	704	0.259
	Control	33	45.67	1507		

DISCUSSION:

There was no notable variation observed in TAS, TOS and OSI of two groups. The few studies generate ureteral stenosis experimentally in animals which were identifying any connection between any renal colic and OS. These studies calculate OS figures for some duration of time. One study was conducted on the rats. They generated one-way hindrance in urine removal in rats. They observed a notable addition in the amount of malonyldialdehyde when analyzed with a healthy group [11]. Malondialdehyde is an oxidant. Investigators noticed a reduction in OS when they formulated full renal ischemia and left it for backflow of blood for small time duration. It reduces the level of superoxide

dismutase, catalase and glutathione peroxide. It also increases the level of lipid peroxidation. The rate of addition is 60 min ischemia -24h backflow blood group [12]. According to our knowledge, a specific time is required for the creation of OS. In a recent study, there is a deficiency of hindrance and proper timing. Due to this OS may also reduce. According to our opinion because of acute pain patients with renal colic should be in attendance to ED. Due to this, the time required for OS to happen does not surpass. According to our observations, it is necessary to count the OS restrictions in differential identification of renal colic.

TAS and MDA levels were noticed prior to operation

in blood samples of about 51 patients in an observation in which a relationship was found between abdominal pain and OS limitations. There were no important variations between the MDA levels were observed. However, a variation was found in the perforated and gangrenous appendicitis group [13]. Another study was arranged to analyze the OS in the sufferers. Appendicitis was identified in patients by this study and it reported that values of TAS reduced notably. While the values of TOS and OSI enhanced appreciably [14].

It was observed that OS mostly enhanced in case of the severe appendix. In a recent study, differentiation of severe appendices renal colic can be made by the lack of increase in OS.

A study was arranged consisting of 81 observers. The patients included in the study were suffering from colorectal carcinogenesis. It was also observed that by increasing the oxidative-antioxidative disease, the colorectal tumour was also enhanced [15]. The analysis on MDA was made by another study. Overall antioxidant level of abdominal pain of 128 patients was observed. It was found that a close relationship was present between abdominal pain and OS [16]. It was known that when the cancer cells liberate oxidant it causes acute pain in the abdominal area. It may also help in the differential identification of severe abdominal pain according to our reports.

The disorders related to gynaecology also cause complexities in identification in disaster services. MDA levels were found to be present in a higher level in females with PCOS [17]. Many other reasons such as endometriosis, mysterious sterility, hydrosalpinx and persistent pregnancy loss also associated with OS [18]. It has been noticed that most of the reasons for abdominal pain may enhance the OS. In the recent study, no enhancement in OS tests originated as a significant feature in variation.

CONCLUSION:

In patients suffering from renal colic, OS experiments within the average range may help in various identification of abdominal pain. It is concluded that OS tests could be used as supplementary tests in the evaluation of renal colic patients when there is no confirmation about the identification with medical symbols.

REFERENCES:

1. Dobashi K, Gosh B, Orak JK, Singh I, Singh AK. Kidney ischemia-reperfusion: Modulation of antioxidant defences. *Mol Cell Biochem* 2000; 205:1-11.

2. Chinard P. Photometric determination of proline and ornithine. *J Biol Chem* 1952; 199:61-5.
3. Kavakli HS, Altintas ND, Yunsur C, Becel S, Tanriverdi F. Diagnostic value of lactate levels in acute appendicitis. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2010; 60:913-5.
4. Skrzydlewska E, Murkowski S, Koda M, Zalewski B, Kanczuga-Koda L, Sulkowska M. Lipid peroxidation and antioxidant status in colorectal cancer. *World J Gastroenterol* 2005; 11:403-6.
5. Chi CH, Shiesh SC, Lin XZ. Total antioxidant capacity and malondialdehyde in acute abdominal pain. *Am J Emerg Med* 2002; 20:79-82
6. Sabuncu T, Vural H, Harma M, Harma M. Oxidative stress in polycystic ovary syndrome and its contribution to the risk of cardiovascular disease *Clin Biochem* 2001;34:407-13.
7. Agarwal A, Gupta S, Sikka S. The role of free radicals and antioxidants in reproduction. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecology* 2006;18: 325-32.
8. Erel O. A novel automated method to measure total antioxidant response against potent free radical reactions. *J Clinical Biochem* 2004; 37:112-9.
9. Erel O. A new automated colourimetric method for measuring total oxidant status. *J. Clinical Biochem* 2005; 47:119-29
10. Harma M, Erel O. Increased oxidative stress in patients with hydatidiform mole. *Swiss Med Wkly* 2003; 133:536-63.
11. Kosecik M, Erel O, Sevinc E, Selek S. Increased oxidative stress in children exposed passively to smoking. *Int. J. Cardiol* 2005; 100:61-4.
12. Tatsuya N. Role of the renin-angiotensin system and nuclear factor-kB in the obstructed kidney of rats with unilateral ureteral obstruction. *Jpn J Pharmacol* 2002; 90:361-4
13. Muslumanoglu AY, Tepeler A. Renal kolik, tan vetedavisi. *Marmara Med J* 2008; 21:87-92.
14. Koçak I. Kolik renal ve akut obstruksiyonlar. *Klinikleri. J Surg Med Sci* 2007; 3:3-8
15. Kim HH, Jo MK, Kwak C, Park SK. Prevalence and epidemiologic characteristics of urolithiasis in Seoul, Korea. *Urology* 2002; 59: 517-21.
16. Akinci M, Esen T, Tellaloglu S. Urinary stone disease: an updated epidemiological study. *Eur Urol* 1991; 20:200-3.
17. Dunnick RN, Sandler CM, Newhouse JH, Amis ES, Jr. Nephrocalcinosis and nephrolithiasis. In: *Textbook of uro-radiology*. 3rd ed. Philadelphia, Pa: Lippincott Williams &Wilkins 2001; pp178-194.
18. Horoz M, Bolukbas C, Bolukbas FF, Sabuncu T, Aslan M, Sarifakiogullari S, et al. Measurement of the total antioxidant response using a novel automated method in subjects with nonalcoholic steatohepatitis. *BMC Gastroenterol* 2005;5:35.